

TITLE

Birth and rebirth of the mosaic in Rome: characterizing the revival of Roman recipes in the 16th -century large-scale wall decorations of the Caetani Chapel, Santa Pudenziana

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ABSTRACT TEXT

This work presents the results of the analytical campaign carried out to support the restoration of the architectural decoration of the Caetani Chapel in the Church of Santa Pudenziana in Rome. Paolo Rossetti produced the wall mosaic in two years (1593-1595), from a sketch by Cesare Roncalli. It represents one of the greatest examples of late 16th-century art in Rome (Catalano et al., 2020). A micro-destructive investigation was carried out to characterise tesserae, mortars and stuccoes from the lunette and the three panels on the vault of the chapel entry. The use of optical microscopy (OM), scanning electron microscopy with energy dispersive X-ray analysis (SEM-EDX), X-ray diffraction (XRD) and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) allowed a better understanding of the original materials and technique. Results

proved that the mosaic layer has been directly mounted on an oil-based stucco layer, likely used to give the artist more time to complete the daily work. Cross-sections observed under OM showed that a paint layer often lies over the stucco. The wide range of materials used for the tesserae demonstrate the great mastery of the mosaic technique Rossetti had. Gold lamina tesserae alternate with a wide range of coloured glass pastes, their dimension changing to gain different visual effects. The vitreous tesserae are made of a silica-soda-lime glass with moderate-to-high lead content, opacified with tin compounds. Stone and terracotta are used to produce tesserae for the flesh tones. Limestone is also used with a great variety of shape, roughness and hue, that further contributes to the vibrant composition.

REFERENCES

Catalano D., Gennari D., Massa V., Moro F., Ciabattini R., Conti L., Medeghini L., Rubino A., Sidoti G., Torre M. (2020) - Restoration and conservation of the mosaics in the Caetani chapel, Church of Santa Pudenziana (Rome): first observations. In: Nardi R., Pugè i Dorca what M. (Eds), What comes to mind when you hear mosaic? Conserving mosaics from ancient to modern, Proceedings of the 13th conference of the International Committee for the Conservation of Mosaics, Barcelona 15-20 October 2017, EDIFIR-Edizioni Firenze, 415-429.

SESSION - ALTERNATIVE SESSION

P7. Geosciences and heritage in a time-lapse: origin, lifetime and future challenges

KEYWORDS

16th-century Rome, mosaic, conservation science